

Transitivity System in Different Spoken Discourses

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to describe the types of processes in transitivity systems used in various spoken discourses and the reasons of using them. This research applied descriptive qualitative design which relies on words to describe the phenomena. The documentation technique was used to achieve the aim of the study. The sources of the data were speech entitled of *I Have a Dream* by Marthin Luther King published in 1963; the sermon on the mount by Jesus of Nazareth published in 2012; and the song entitled of *You Raise Me Up* by Josh Groban in 2003. The findings showed that there were six types of processes in speech and sermon but not all types of them were used in the song. The types of processes found in the speech were 139 processes; dominantly was material process which was 60 (43%). There were 76 processes in sermon, and dominantly were 44 (57, 8%) material process; while there were 42 processes in the song; dominantly was 25 (59, 6%) material process. There were 6 reasons of using types of processes in different spoken discourses: 1) physical actions, 2) thinking actions, 3) identifying features, 4) speaking actions, 5) physiological actions and 6) actions that signal the existence of something/someone. It could be concluded that material process are found to be the most dominant in spoken discourse as it represents the process of doing.

Keywords: *transitivity, process, spoken discourse*

Introduction

Systemic Functional Linguistics is a theory about language as a resource for making meaning which is situated in a context of situation and a context of culture. This theory also stresses on communication. In other words, it concerns with the relation between language and context in which it is used. It is known as meta-function. Saragih (2010:1) stated that meta-functions consists of 3 functions, namely; (1) Interpersonal function, (2) Ideational function, and (3) Textual function. First, *Interpersonal function* means that language is used to interact with others. Second, *Ideational function* means that the language is used to organize, to understand and to express our perceptions of the world and consciousness. Ideational function are divided into two, they are *experiential function*, where language is used to express experience, and *logical function* is encoded in the

grammar as complex unit in which the clauses should be related each other and can take conclusion logically based on the clauses described in the text. Third, *Textual function* means that the language is used to organize experience. As with the clause as exchange, there is one major system of grammatical choice involved in this kind of meaning, this is *the system of transitivity or process type*.

Some of the studies about transitivity were conducted especially in relation to the spoken discourse. One of them was Harwiyati (2016) who found that all types of transitivity processes appeared in Joko Widodo's Speech and relational process was dominantly used in the utterances. Hemas and Ariyanti (2016) found that Emma Watson dominantly used mental process followed by material process in her speech. The underlying reason of its use was because she wanted to influence people to have more correct views of feminist movement. These processes were used to get the listeners' sympathy by showing her emotion, thinking, and inclination. These researches were just focused on the spoken discourse such as speech. Meanwhile, spoken discourse was also varied in forms such as speech, sermon, songs, etc. Therefore, a study in relation to these various forms of spoken discourse needs to be conducted in order to get a wider horizon of how the transitivity of processes works in these forms.

Method

This research applied descriptive qualitative design which focused on words rather than numbers. In some cases, numbers are used to indicate the frequency of each category in transcripts or the extent to which a form of action occurs. This study was conducted with the aim of analyzing the use of processes in transitivity system in different spoken discourses through speech, sermon, and song.

The source of the data was speech entitled of *I Have a Dream* by Martin Luther King in 1963; the sermon of the mount by Jesus of Nazareth which published in 2012. This sermon was a collection of sayings and teachings of Jesus of Nazareth, which emphasized his moral teaching found in the Gospel of Matthew. It was the first of the Five Discourses of Matthew and took place relatively early in the Ministry of Jesus after he had been baptized by John the Baptist and preached in Galilee; and the song entitled *You Raise Me Up* by Josh Groban in 2003.

The data was analyzed by following these steps: (1) reading the transcript of the whole data source, (2) dividing the transcript of speech, sermon and song into clauses, (3)

identifying and classifying the data that belongs to the transitivity system, (4) analyzing the data that belongs to the processes in transitivity system, (5) identifying each spoken discourse's reason in using types of processes in transitivity system, (6) drawing the conclusion.

Result

Types of Processes in Transitivity System in Different Spoken Discourses

Theoretically, there are six types of processes in transitivity system proposed by Halliday in Saragih (2006:03) namely Material process, Mental process, Relational process, Verbal process, Behavioral process, Existential process.

Empirically, all of these types of processes were found in spoken discourses such as speech and sermon. However, there were only material, mental, relational processes were found in the song. The analysis of the processes in different spoken discourses can be seen in this following data:

The speech entitled *I Have a Dream* by Martin Luther King

Data 1

When	the architects of our republic	wrote	the magnificent words of the Constitution and the Declaration of Independence
	P1: Actor	Pro: Material	P2: Goal

The word “*wrote*” belongs to material process since the word expresses physical action, and it also has two participants namely; the architects of our republic (actor) and *the magnificent words of the Constitution and the Declaration of Independence* (goal).

Data 2

And	those who	Hope	that the Negro needed to blow off steam
	Senser	Pro: Mental	Phenomenon

The word “*Hope*” belongs to mental process since the word expresses the feeling or the thinking of people, and it also has two participants, namely *Those who* its mean some people (senser) and *that the Negro needed to blow off steam*(phenomenon).

Data 3

I	Am	happy to join with you	Today
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Carrier	Pro: Relational	Attribute	Cir: Loc: Temporal
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The word “*am*” belongs to relational process since the word assigns a quality of someone feeling, and it also has two participants, namely *I* (Carrier) and *happy to join with you* (Attribute).

Data 4

I	Say	to you	Today	my friends
P1: Sayer	Pro: Verbal	P2: Receive	Circumstance	P2: Receive

The word “*say*” belongs to verbal process since the word symbolically signaling that some people is saying, and it also has two participants, namely *I* (sayer) and *to you* (Receiver).

Data 5

One hundred years later	the Negro	Lives	on a lonely island of poverty in the midst of a vast ocean of material prosperity
Cir: Loc: Temporal	Behaver	Pro: Behavioral	Cir: Loc: Spatial

The word “*Lives*” belongs to behavioral process since the word focus on how the participant behave, and it also has one participant, namely *The Negro* (Behaver)

Data 6

That	there are	insufficient funds	in the great vaults of opportunity of this nation
	Pro: Existential	Existent	Cir: Loc: Temporal

The word “*there are*” belongs to existential process which is known by the word “there” and the word represent that something exist and it also has one participant namely *insufficient funds* (existent).

The sermon of the mount by Jesus of Nazareth

Data 7

Lay not up	for yourselves treasures	upon earth
Pro: Material	Goal	Cir: Location

The word “*Lay not up*” is a material process since the word expresses activity that people lay not up for yourselves treasures upon earth. In data seven just found one participant namely *for yourselves treasures* (Goal).

Data 8

And why	Behold	Thou	the mote that is in thy brother's eye
	Pro: Mental	Senser	Phenomenon

The word “*behold*” is a mental process since the word expresses how someone perceives through him/her sense, and it also has two participants, namely *thou* (senser) and *the mote that is in thy brother's eye* (phenomenon).

Data 9

For where your treasure	Is
Token	Pro: Relational

The word “*is*” belongs to relational process since the word expresses identifying, and it also has one participants, namely *for where your treasure* (Token).

Data 10

For with what judgment	Ye	Judge
Verbiage	Sayer	Pro: Verbal

The word “*judge*” is a verbal process since the word symbolically signaling that someone is giving the opinion or estimate with other people and it also has two participants, namely *ye* (sayer) and *For with what judgment* (verbiage).

Data 10

And	Ye	shall find
	Behavior	Pro: Behavioral

The word “*shall find*” is a behavioral process since the word focus on how the participant behave which namely *ye* (Bahever).

Data 11

Or	what man	is there	of you
	Existent	Pro: Existential	

The word “*is there*” belongs to existential process since the word represent that something exists, and it also has one participant, namely *what man* (Existent).

The Song Entitled *You Raise Me Up* by Josh Groban

Data 12

Until	You	Come
	Actor	Pro: Material

The word “*come*” belongs to material process since the word expresses activity that someone comes and it also has one participant, namely *you* (actor).

Data 13

And	my heart	Burdened	Be
	Senser	Pro: Mental	Phenomenon

The word “*burdened*” belongs to mental process since the word expresses how someone feel burdened in her/his heart and it also has two participants, namely *my heart* (Senser) and *be* (Phenomenon).

Data 14

When	I	Am	Down
	Carrier	Pro: Relational	Attribute

The word “*am*” belongs to relational process since the word expresses attributive, and it also has two participants, namely *I* (Carrier) and *down* (Attribute). The list of the total number of processes in different spoken discourses is presented in table 3.1.

Table 3.1 Types of Processes in Transitivity System in different Spoken Discourses

No	Spoken discourses Types of process	Speech		Sermon		Song	
		Freq	Per	Freq	Per	Freq	Per
1.	Material	60	43%	44	57,8%	25	59,6%
2.	Mental	12	8,5%	9	12%	1	2,3%
3.	Relational	48	34,2%	4	5,2%	16	38,1%
4.	Verbal	6	4,2%	12	15,8%	-	
5.	Behavioral	10	7,1%	3	4%	-	
6.	Existential	4	3%	4	5,2%	-	
Total		140	100%	76	100%	42	100%

The Reasons of Using Types of Processes in Transitivity System in different Spoken Discourses

According to Halliday (2008) transitivity system is composed of six processes that represent human experience in terms of: physical and physiological actions (Material and Behavioral), thinking and speaking actions (Mental and Verbal) and actions that signal the existence of something/someone and their identifying features (Existential and Relational).

The examples of the data about the reasons of using the types of processes in transitivity system which were used in different spoken discourses can be seen as follows:

The speech entitled *I Have a Dream* by Martin Luther King and Sermon of the mount by Jesus of Nazareth.

Physical actions.

Data 15

<u>Signed</u>	<u>The Emancipation Proclamation</u>
Pro: Material	Goal

This data belongs to physical actions because the word “signed” related to the real action done by the participant one call the actor since the word express activity that people signed the emancipation proclamation. In the speech entitled I Have a Dream by Martin Luther King, material process found as the most dominant process, it is because the speech indicates the activities or events and physical action about the historical background of the hatred and racial discrimination from which the Negro people had been suffering, the demand and the reasons for a struggle of justice.

Actions their identifying features.

Data 16

<u>This note</u>	<u>was</u>	<u>a promise</u>
Token	Pro: Relational	value

This data belongs to actions their identifying features because the verb “was” expresses identifying of “this note” as participants I and “a promise” as participant II. In the speech entitled I Have a Dream by Martin Luther King, relational process became the second dominant process, it is because the speech assigns a quality of someone feeling, and states of having their dreams.

Thinking actions.

Data 17

<u>Who</u>	<u>are asking</u>	<u>the devotees of civil rights</u>
Senser	Pro: Mental	Phenomenon

This data belongs to thinking actions because the verb “are asking” described as states of thinking or psychological events. In the speech entitled I Have a Dream by Martin Luther King, mental process became the third dominant process.

Physiological actions.

Data 18

that my four little will one day live in a nation
children
Behaver Cir: Spatial **Pro: Behavioral** Cir; Temporal

This data belongs to physiological actions because the verb “live” represents human experience in terms of physiological actions. In the speech entitled I Have a Dream by Martin Luther King, behavioral process became the fourth dominant process.

Speaking actions.

Data 19

I must say to my people
Sayer **Pro: Verbal** Receive

This data belongs to speaking actions because the verb “must say” shown activities related to speaking. In the speech entitled I Have a Dream by Martin Luther King, verbal process became the fifth dominant process.

Actions that signal the existence of something/someone.

Data 20

there is an invigorating autumn of freedom and equality
Pro: Existential Existent

This data belongs to actions that signal the existence of something/someone because the verb “there is” represented that something exists or happens. In the speech entitled I Have a Dream by Martin Luther King, existential process became the sixth dominant process.

The Song Entitled *You Raise Me Up* by Josh Groban

Physical actions.

Data 21

You raise me up
Actor **Pro: Material** goal

This data belongs to physical actions because the verb “raise” related to the real action done or physical by the participant one called the actor and participant two called goal, in the Song Entitled *You Raise Me Up* by Josh Groban, material

Based on the table above, it is shown that in the all of the spoken discourses namely the speech entitled I Have a Dream by Martin Luther King, the sermon of the mount by Jesus of Nazareth, and the song entitled You Raise Me Up by Josh Groban, Material processes are found to be the most dominant, the reasons because all of the spoken discourses indicates events and activities that happen in the outside world of human beings. The result of data analysis in table 4.2.2, shown that spoken discourses factor seem influence the use of the types of processes in transitivity system, it shown that all of the speakers use the same number of material process, mental process and almost all of the ranks of using the types of processes were same.

Discussion

There are six types of processes in transitivity system were found in the speech entitled I have a dream by Martin Luther King in 1963, namely: (1) material process, (2) mental process, (3) relational process, (4) verbal process, (5) behavioral process, (6) existential process. It contents 60 (43%) material processes, 12(8, 5%) mental processes, 48 (34, 2%) relational processes, 6(4, 2%) verbal processes, 10(7, 1%) behavioral processes, 4 (3%) existential processes. In the sermon of the mount by Jesus of Nazareth which published in 2012, there are also 6 (six) types of processes in transitivity system found, namely: (1) material process, (2) mental process, (3) relational process, (4) verbal process, (5) behavioral process, (6) existential process. It contents 44 (57, 8%) material processes, 9 (12%) mental processes, 4 (5, 2%) relational processes, 12 (15, 8%) verbal processes, 3 (4%) behavioral processes, 4(5, 2%) existential processes.

In the song entitled You Raise Me Up by Josh Groban in 2003, there are not all of the types of transitivity system found because the songhas lyric limitation, andthere isrepetition of wordsinthe song. And just 3 (three) types of processes in transitivity system found. They are: (1) material process, (2) mental process, (3) relational process. It contents 25 (59, 6%) material processes, 1 (2, 3%) mental process, 16 (38, 1%) relational processes.

There are 6 reasons of using types of processes in transitivity system in different spoken discourses, namely; 1) physical actions, 2) thinking actions 3) identifying features 4) speaking actions 5) physiological actions 6) actions that signal the existence of something/someone. In this study, it was figured out that in the speech entitled I have a dream by Martin Luther King in 1963 were 60 examples of physical actions, 12 examples of thinking actions, 48examples of identifying features, 6 examples of speaking actions,

10 examples of physiological actions, 4 examples of actions that signal the existence of something/someone. In the sermon of the mount by Jesus of Nazareth which published in 2012 were 44 examples of physical actions, 9 examples of thinking actions, 4 examples of identifying features, 12 examples of speaking actions, 3 examples of physiological actions, and 4 examples of actions that signal the existence of something/someone. In the song entitled You Raise Me Up by Josh Groban in 2003 were 25 examples of physical actions, 1 example of thinking actions, 16 examples of identifying features.

This study related to Halliday (2008) stated that transitivity system is composed of six processes that represent human experience in terms of: physical and physiological actions (Material and Behavioral), thinking and speaking actions (Mental and Verbal) and actions that signal the existence of something/someone and their identifying features (Existential and Relational).

References

- Halliday, M.A.K. (2008). *An introduction to functional grammar* (3rd Ed.). London: Edward Arnold.
- Harwiyati, R. (2016). Transitivity System on Joko Widodo's Speech at the APEC CEO Summit on November 10th, 2014, in Beijing, China. *Premise Journal*. 5(1), 161-171.
- Hemas, S.M., and Ariyanti, L. (2016). Transitivity and Ideology in Emma Watson's Speech for the *Heforshe* Campaign (Critical Discourse Analysis). *Language Horizon*, 1(1), 27-37.
- Saragih, A. (2006). *Introducing Systemic Functional Grammar*. Medan: FBS UNIMED (Unpublished).
- _____. (2010). *Discourse Analysis: A Systemic Functional Approach: The Analysis of Texts*. Medan: FBS UNIMED (Unpublished).